

A Study on Treating Social Degradation in the Select Works of Lillian Hellman

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 8

Special Issue: 1

Month: December

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-2645

E-ISSN: 2582-3531

Impact Factor: 4.110

Citation:

Karpagajothi, S.
“A Study on Treating Social Degradation in the Select Works of Lillian Hellman.”
Shanlax International Journal of English, vol. 8, no. S1, 2019, pp. 9–11.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3599834>

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Hellman uses realistic technique to narrate the plays. In realistic technique, the characters mirror the ordinary men in real life. They undergo all the sufferings of real men and lives in social condition of a particular age. Doris V. Falk in Lillian Hellman expresses his idea about realism. Falk notes that realism “assumes that there is a certain logical connection between events; that all actions have consequences” (32).

Falk observes that the present state of a society, depicted in a realism drama is the consequence of people’s past actions. In Hellman’s plays, transformation occurs in characters because of their past actions. Unlike melodramatic heroines, Hellman’s female characters are ambitious, evil, weak, dominant, and working-class women. In one or the other way, the female characters become victims in the hands of evil. Only few characters are depicted as good souls. Hellman’s wicked characters are always given importance.

According to Timothy J. Wiles in “Lillian Hellman’s American Political Theatre: The Thirties and Beyond,” she states, “Hellman’s villainous characters certainly entertain us with their sardonic humor and extravagant ruthlessness in treating others in a purely instrumental way, and their crimes do expose the need for a socialist counterreaction” (166).

Apart from the central theme in each play, Hellman analyzed the concept of evil in all her plays. According to Hellman, the Great Depression and Capitalism have affected the society and its people to a greater extent. Hellman’s major themes: economic independence, evil, and importance of morality apparently show her concern for social consciousness. Hellman wrote all her plays between 1930s to 1960s. Yet, the themes dealt by Hellman could be traced even today. The present society faces the problems of lies, gossips, greed, jealous and corruption.

The first play taken for study, *The Children’s Hour* uncovers the power of lies and gossips that destroys two innocent women, who

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are falsely accused as lesbians. The society plays a major role in spoiling the two teachers' lives. Without investigating the truth, people believe a child's lie and immediately they gossip about the teachers' unnatural relationship. The false accusation destroys the two protagonists-Karen and Martha's profession and their respect in the society. In addition, even the family member of the accused does not like to involve in a lesbian case. Martha's aunt Mrs. Lily Mortar does not go to court to testify about the false charge. Therefore, the society ill-treats the people who are accused of lesbianism.

Hellman underscores the upper-class people's involvement in destroying the two teachers' lives. An upper-class rich old woman Mrs. Amelia Tilford, who helped these two teachers financially, spreads the news of Karen and Martha's unnatural relationship to the parents of students who studies at Wright-Dobie school. She thinks that she has taken the correct decision of withdrawing all the students from the school and keeps them separate from lesbian teachers. Others also believe the accusation, when the news is received from a wealthy upper-class woman.

The second play taken for study, *The Little Foxes* speaks about people's greed for money. The play also exposes the evil effects of capitalism in the society. The Hubbard siblings'-Ben, Regina and Oscar-thirst for money destroys their family.

This play clearly pictures a degraded society and its wicked people's domination over weaker section of the society and on women. In this play, women possess no power and the male members of the family oppress them. Regina, wishes to settle in Chicago. However, her ambition to settle in Chicago makes her to kill Horace and blackmail her brothers. Insufficient material needs make people to do evil things. In order to acquire money, the capitalism society even makes women as commodities. Men marry women to get her family's property and not out of love.

Many people wrongly understand Hellman's perception of Hubbards and her original intention. Lillian Hellman was disappointed in the frequent reception of Regina and her brothers as simple villains in a melodrama. In *Pentimento* she says that, "I had meant the audience to recognize some part of themselves in the money dominated Hubbards; I had not meant people to think of them as villains to whom they had no connection" (168). She tries to express that everyone has to fight greed and other components of evil, which dominates him or her to create a good society.

In capitalistic society, the owners focus on only to increase their wealth. They have no concern for their employees. The money minded Hubbards cheat the African American people. The slaves and low-class people become poorer day by day and the owners increase their riches every day. The poor have the chance to receive salary only during a particular season. The other times, the people have to starve and face death. Through this play, Hellman disclose the living condition of people.

One must not conclude that Hellman focuses only on the evil elements in people and society. Bill Moyers, in an interview with Hellman, when asked about her frequent perception on evil, Hellman snapped with an answer that, "I'm a moral writer and looking at evil is a form of morality, isn't it?" (123). Hellman places her message in the young minds.

She makes the readers to understand his or her social condition and how he is influenced by the people-family, friends and the society. One must not let go of the morality despite the suffering undergone by them. Once a person understands his environment, it kindles compassion, makes him to work for the betterment of people and ultimately brings a positive change in the society.

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